

Patriotism - Criteria of High Values

Pardaev Jaloliddin Akhrorkul ugli¹

¹ Doctoral student, Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

Annotation:

This article is dedicated to educating the young generation in the idea of patriotism, which is the main criterion of our national values, "the Fatherland is great, the duty is sacred". The purpose of the article is to inculcate the courage and heroism of our ancestors in the fight against fascism in the Second World War, along with our ancestors like Tomaris, Spitamen, Jalaliddin Manguberdi and Amir Temur, who fought for the freedom and independence of our country, in the consciousness of the young generation.

Keywords: National value, patriotism, era of globalization, World War II, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, Uzbek heroes, Jurakul Toraev, Dubrova village, Jurakhon Usmanov, Eshonkul Ismailov.

INTRODUCTION

In today's era of globalization, the armed conflicts and confrontations taking place in different parts of the world, including in our region, are facing us the most important and important thing is to educate the youth of our country in the spirit of patriotism, the conceptual idea of "Motherland is great, duty is sacred" and in the spirit of high spiritual and moral values. is putting urgent issues that cannot be delayed.[1]

In carrying out this task, our national values and the fact that the protection of the Motherland is an honorable and sacred duty, as well as the rich spiritual heritage of our great ancestors, the contributions of generals such as Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur to the development of world civilization and military art, should be taught to young people.

MAIN PART

In this place, along with our ancestors like Tumaris, Shiroq, Spitamen, Jaloliddin Manguberdi, Amir Temur, who fought for the independence and freedom of our country, to inculcate in the

consciousness of the young generation the bravery and heroism of our ancestors in the battles against fascism in the Second World War is appropriate.

In the Second World War, which caused the greatest number of victims per head of humanity, the brave sons of the Uzbek people fought valiantly against the scourge of fascism, among all nations. However, in recent years, not enough attention has been paid to studying the bravery and heroism of Uzbek soldiers in the Second World War and covering them in the media. In this regard, our honorable president Sh.M. Mirziyoyev expressed the following thoughts in his speech dedicated to the "Remembrance and Appreciation" day on May 9, 2019; "Using today's opportunity, I would like to make a proposal to our historical scholars, literary and artistic figures, and our general public. I think it's time to create new works about the heroism of our ancestors who participated in this terrible war, including preparing and publishing a perfect book-album based on accurate historical documents" [2].

The multinational people of Uzbekistan also showed true courage and selflessness and made a great contribution to the victory over fascism. In particular, about 2 million of our compatriots participated in the battles, and more than 500 thousand of them died like heroes. At the same time, during the war, our republic became one of the important supply centers for supplying food, clothing, weapons and other means necessary for the front. In particular, our compatriots took more than 1.5 million old people, women and young children who were relocated to Uzbekistan from the regions where the fighting is going on, and showed them incomparable care in difficult times.

More than 500,000 Uzbek fighters died in the war, i.e. one out of three of those mobilized to the front, and more than 60,000 of our compatriots returned disabled. More than 120,000 war participants from Uzbekistan were awarded orders and medals. 301 of them were awarded the title of Hero of the Soviet Union. [3]

In this article, the bravery and bravery of several Heroes of the Soviet Union from Jizzakh, who were awarded such a high title, are covered based on information from archives and military literature. One of them is Hero of the Soviet Union Jurakul Turayev.

Jurakul Turayev was born on March 20, 1922 in the village of Kaliya Molkanlik, Jizzakh District (now Sharaf Rashidov District), Jizzakh Region. In 1941, he was drafted into the ranks of the Soviet Army. Since 1941, he participated in battles on various fronts, including the Bryansk, Central and Belarusian fronts, and was seriously wounded twice.

From December 1943, junior sergeant Jurakul Turayev participated in military battles as a marksman in the 1007th light artillery regiment of the 12th artillery division of the 46th light artillery brigade of the 65th army of the Belorussian front.

On December 21, 1943, the 2nd battery, in which junior sergeant Jurakul Turayev served, was assigned the task of protecting the strategically important hill number 143.3 near the village of Dubrova, Svetlogorsk district, Gomel region of the present Republic of Belarus, from enemy attack. In the defense of the hill, the bravery of the marksman Jurakul Turayev, who heroically entered the battle against 27 enemy tanks and thousands of infantrymen, played an important role. In this battle, Junior Sergeant Jurakul Turayev knocked out 5 enemy tanks. Jurakul Turayev, who was seriously wounded and concussed, did not leave the battlefield and continued to fire against enemy tanks. Even though he was wounded, he brought a shell and shot the cannon and knocked out the enemy's fifth tank. After that, as a result of a strong explosion, he lost consciousness. 143.3 hills were saved thanks to the heroism of Jurakul Turayev and the soldiers of the 2nd battery, who regained consciousness in the field medical battalion. [4]

Before this battle, 12 enemy tanks, 2 "Ferdinand" heavy self-propelled guns and a number of infantrymen were destroyed by Sergeant Jurakul Turayev. Junior Sergeant Jurakul Turayev was

awarded the title of Hero of the Soviet Union and the Order of the Golden Star by the decision of the Presidium of the Family Soviet of the USSR dated March 29, 1944 for his heroism in this battle.

On May 7, 2017, a memorial monument was erected in his honor on the hill near the village of Dubrova, Svetlogorsk region, Gomel region, Gomel region, Republic of Belarus, where Jurakul Turayev was a hero. [5]

Another hero of the Second World War, a fighter of the 1st Belorussian Front, 240th Rifle Regiment of the 8th Army, Eshankul Ismailov from Gallaarol, who is remembered with great pride. Eshankul Ismailov was born on March 1, 1902 in the village of Turk, Gallaarol district, Jizzakh region.

He was drafted into military service in 1942, and from 1943, he fought on the 3rd Ukrainian and 1st Belorussian fronts. In the battles for the Dnieper, Odessa and Belarus took part in offensive operations. In January 1945, E. Ismailov showed exceptional heroism and example in the battles to capture the city-fortress of Poznan. E. Ismailov destroyed several enemy checkpoints and about 40 enemy soldiers in the battle. Inspired by the heroism of E. Ismailov, the battalion attacked and the enemy hospital was captured with about 400 wounded soldiers. [6]

In the subsequent battles for Poznan, E. Ismailov killed about 20 enemies. On January 29, 1945, severely wounded E. Ismailov did not leave the battlefield and continued the battle. According to the decision of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR on May 31, 1945, Eshankul Ismailov was awarded the title of Hero of the Soviet Union and the "Golden Star" medal. [7]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Another one of the heroes of this glorious past is Jurakhan Usmanov. Jurakhan Usmanov was born on February 12, 1922 in the village of Savat, Yangiabad District, Jizzakh Region, in a peasant family. He was drafted into the ranks of the Red Army in 1942, and from March he participated in the battles against the enemy in the ranks of the active army [8].

On September 29, 1943, senior sergeant Jurakhan Usmanov, the assistant platoon commander of the 237th rifle regiment, showed heroism when crossing the Soj River near the village of Karpovka, Gomel region of the present Republic of Belarus. Senior sergeant Jurakhan Usmanov, who was one of the first to cross the river, repelled 13 enemy counterattacks with his 8 surviving comrades and ensured the passage of the main forces of the Red Army. Jurakhan Usmanov was seriously wounded in this battle [9].

By the decision of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the USSR on January 15, 1944, senior sergeant Jurakhan Usmanov was awarded the title of Hero of the Soviet Union and the "Golden Star" medal for his personal bravery in the fight against the invaders and exemplary performance of the assigned military mission.

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CONCLUSION

To sum up, it is important to promote and promote among young people the heroism of the veterans of the Second World War and behind the front lines, which they showed at the front and behind the front lines, in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism. Such activities will give a high result if they are carried out together with spiritual and educational activities in the neighborhood, schools and higher education institutions. The participation of veterans of the Second World War

behind the front is of great importance to the events organized in this regard, especially in the education of students of higher educational institutions in the spirit of patriotism.

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